

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

A Spectrophotometric Determination of the Dissociation Constant of Bisulphate Ion in Aqueous Solution

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In course of our determination of the standard potential of mercury, mercurous sulphate electrode in mixed solvents, we needed the dissociation constant of the bisulphate ion in such media. There is no report of the value of the dissociation constant of the bisulphate ion in mixed solvent, although a number of workers have determined the constant in water. We examined critically the different methods that have been adopted in aqueous medium.

Young and Irish¹ have summarised the values of the constant determined by various methods. Recently Christensen *et al.*² have reported a calorimetric determination. It has been usually assumed that the best value for the dissociation constant of the bisulphate ion comes from the unpublished spectrophotometric work by Young, Klotz and Singleterry³. The principal reason is that ΔH derived from such measurements at different temperatures by these authors agreed with the calorimetric value of Pitzer⁴. Young, Klotz and Singleterry compared the optical density of a solution of methyl orange containing HCl and sodium sulphate with a similar solution of methyl orange containing only HCl and sodium chloride or barium chloride to give the same ionic strength as the other solution. From the change in the optical density due to the change in pH of the first solution resulting from the combination of H^+ and $SO_4^{''}$ ions and the pH of the original acid solution the K's have been calculated. For methyl orange they had to use the reference solution with an acidity around $pH=3$. Since the pH range of methyl orange is 3.1-4.4 and that of bromocresol green is 4.0-5.6, the acidity of the reference solution in case of the latter indicator can be made much lower and as such the relative change in the pH resulting from the combination of H^+ and $SO_4^{''}$ will be larger. Therefore, the change in optical density will be larger and hence the experimental accuracy attained will be better.

We are reporting here the value of the dissociation constant of the bisulphate ion determined spectrophotometrically using bromocresol green as an indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromocresol green indicator solution was made by dissolving 0.4 gm. of the indicator (B.D.H.) per litre. Suspended impurities were got rid of by filtration.

1. Young, T.F. and Irish, D.E., *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 13, 435.
2. Christensen, J.J., Izatt, R. M., Hansen, L. D., and Patridge, J.A., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 2003.
3. "Electrolytic solutions" by Robinson & Stokes, Butterworths, London, 2nd edn, 1959, p. 435.
4. Pitzer, K. S., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2365.

Sodium chloride (E. Merck, G.R.) was used to maintain the ionic strength. Barium chloride was a B.D.H. Analar sample. Sodium sulphate (Baker & Adamson make) was dried at 130° for three to four hours and the anhydrous sample was kept in a desiccator for use.

Reference solution was prepared by adding known amounts of indicator, sodium chloride or barium chloride and HCl (to keep the acidity around pH 4). The pH of the reference solution was calculated from the known concentration of the acid added using limiting Debye-Huckel equation. The other solution contained the same amount HCl, the indicator and sodium sulphate.

The optical densities of the solutions were measured with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer. All the experimental solutions were prepared in duplicate and their optical densities checked within 0.5%. Temperature was 25 ± 0.1°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dissociation constant, K, for

was calculated by the method of Klotz and Singletary. The values of K at different ionic strengths using sodium chloride and also barium chloride to adjust the same, are given below.

Ionic strength	0.015	0.018	0.0225	0.033	0.0405	0.048	0.06	0.072
K × 10 ⁴ using NaCl	89.6	91.6	88.2	82.2	80.7	80.6	73.2	77.6
Using BaCl ₂	107.9		104	103.4	105.2	102.8	108.6	

The values of K were plotted against ionic strength and extrapolated to zero ionic strength to obtain the thermodynamic dissociation constant. This was also obtained by the method of least squares.

One interesting point, which is worth noting, is the difference in slopes in the two extrapolations. In case of barium chloride the slope is very small, possibly indicating that where an attempt is made to prepare a solution of the same ionic strength it may be better to use same valence-type ions.

The extrapolated value of K is 0.0097 in case of sodium chloride and 0.0104 in case of barium chloride. The difference may be due to indicator-salt effect. But because this difference is within the limits of experimental errors, we prefer to report for 'K' the average value of 0.0101 ± 0.0004.

The present value, using bromocresol-green as an indicator, is in agreement with the values in literature. The values of K in mixed solvents using this indicator will be reported in due course.

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